

Design of *Megabalanus coccopoma* - Specific DNA primers for the detection of planktonic larvae of this invasive barnacle species in Shenzhen

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Abstract

The issue of invasive species has become much more relevant in recent years, as global trade has completely breached the usual barriers separating different ecosystems. These invasive species can cause negative impacts on both the native ecosystem and the local economy. Recently, one important invasive species has been the titan acorn barnacle *Megabalanus coccopoma*, which is indigenous to the tropical Pacific coasts of the Americas, and has become established in many locations ranging from tropical to subtropical and temperate coasts worldwide. In this paper, barnacle-specific and *M. coccopoma*-specific DNA primers were designed and validated, in an attempt to design a method to monitor the presence of *M. coccopoma* larvae in the water column. These primers were also used to test plankton samples around Shenzhen, China, where *M. coccopoma* is suspected to be established. Using the experiments, the barnacle-specific primers were determined to be in fact not barnacle-specific, but some of the *M. coccopoma*-specific primers were shown to be specific to *M. coccopoma*. However, the tests on plankton samples were inconclusive, as no larvae of *M. coccopoma* were discovered, but the range of samples taken was very limited. With more extensive surveys, these primers could potentially be used in ports to avoid the introduction of unwanted species, especially *M. coccopoma*, or to monitor *M. coccopoma* in areas where it has already been introduced to determine future actions in response to this threat.

1. Introduction

Invasive species have become a major problem as globalization of trade has spread many species across the world. An invasive species is usually a non-native species which multiplies out of control and causes economic and ecological damage in a new environment [1]. Invasive species can disrupt local ecosystems and drive native species to extinction through competition for resources and hybridization with related native species [2]. Before becoming truly

invasive, species usually undergo several stages, including introduction, where the species arrives in a new environment, and establishment, where the species begins to interact with the local ecosystem and starts to reproduce and multiply, potentially to such an extent that it becomes invasive [3]. The progression of potentially invasive species through these stages, particularly whether they are established or not, should be monitored by scientists.

Currently, many efforts to monitor potentially invasive species rely on molecular methods to detect their presence. These methods are more sensitive, require less complicated sample collection processes, and cause less disturbance to the local environment than traditional surveying methods, which require the collection of individual animals, and thus affect the ecosystem while being unreliable with low densities of individuals. These molecular methods involve polymerase chain reaction (PCR) to amplify DNA and gene sequencing for species identification. DNA primers are needed to perform PCR, to which the polymerase binds in order to duplicate the sample DNA. Species-specific primers can often be used to monitor individual invasive species. However, very few species-specific primers have been created, and primers are often not available for the target species.

An invasive species that has become very problematic in recent years is *Megabalanus coccopoma* (Darwin, 1854), the titan acorn barnacle. From the tropical Pacific coast of the Americas, *M. coccopoma* has been introduced to Japan [4], Australia [4], the Atlantic coast of the Southeastern United States [5], and the North Sea [6]. *M. coccopoma* competes with native barnacles and other sessile species for resources, potentially driving them to local extinction [7]. It also attaches to human infrastructure.

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This is especially problematic when it attaches to ship hulls, as its large size causes a significant increase in drag forces on the ship, increasing the amount of fuel the ship requires [8]. The lack of species-specific primers was a major challenge for monitoring *M. coccopoma*.

In this investigation, a primer specific to *M. coccopoma* was designed using the 18S ribosomal DNA (18S rRNA) and cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (COI) genes and tested. These genes were selected because they are generally quite conserved among species, enabling the design of a primer for all barnacles while still having a high enough mutation rate for designing primers to distinguish other barnacles from *M. coccopoma*. Primers specific to all barnacle species were also designed using the 18S and COI genes to be used as a preliminary check, which could be used to further confirm the results obtained by using the *M. coccopoma*-specific primers, as it is impossible for *M. coccopoma* to be present in a sample while barnacles are absent. These primers will enable the detection of *M. coccopoma* larvae in plankton samples, which allows the verification of whether or not it is reproducing and therefore established in a new environment. The primers tested could be useful for monitoring the status of *M. coccopoma* in various regions of the world and for choosing appropriate measures to reduce its spread.

2. Method

2.1. Validation of Barnacle 18S Specific (Barn-18s) Primers

Barnacle 18S-specific primers (Barn-18s) were designed based on the 18S rDNA sequences of Cirripedia, Decapoda and Isopoda species, which were downloaded from the NCBI nucleotide database. The sequences were aligned using the MUSCLE algorithm on MEGA 7. The alignment was searched manually for barnacle-specific regions. The length, guanine-cytosine (GC) content and melting temperature (T_m) of the barnacle-specific regions were calculated using the [NEB Tm Calculator](#). The sequences with the most suitable length, GC content and T_m were chosen and made into candidate primers. The reverse primers were designed by reverse complementing barnacle-specific regions using [Reverse Complement on Bioinformatics.org](#).

Ibla cumingi and *Capitulum mitella* were collected from the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (22.336615°N, 114.269210°E). *Megabalanus tintinnabulum* was harvested by local fishermen from the rocky shore along the coast of Fuzhou, China.

The samples were dissected and muscle tissue was removed from each sample. The samples were ground down by homogenizing with 0.1 mm glass beads, and 75% alcohol was added to aid the process. The equipment was washed with pure water after grinding each sample. The resulting liquid was placed into 1.5 ml centrifuge tubes.

The Biospin Marine Animal Genomic Extraction Kit was used to extract the DNA following the instructions that came with the extraction kit. The centrifuge used was the Bioridge TG16.5 Tabletop High-Speed Centrifuge. After the DNA was extracted, the Miulab ND-100C Ultra-Micro Ultraviolet-Visible Spectrophotometer was used to measure the concentration of DNA. All samples had a concentration of at least 10 ng/μL, so none of them were discarded.

Aside from the samples just prepared, previously extracted DNA from 1 bivalve (*Atrina pectinata*), 1 gastropod (*Rapana venosa*), 1 cephalopod (*Octopus vulgaris*), 1 decapod (*Pandalus platyceros*), and 1 fish (*Thunnus obesus*) was also used for PCR. 22 μL of water was added to every tube. 1 μL of forward primer and 1 μL of reverse primer were added to each tube. 1 μL of DNA template solution was added to each tube. The PCR mix was the Vazyme 2 x Phanta Max Master Mix (Dye Plus). 25 μL was added to each tube. The contents of the tubes were mixed using the Miulab MIX-25P Mini Mixer. The tubes were then placed for around 5 seconds in the Miulab MINI-6K Mini Centrifuge. The tubes were then placed in the ETC811 Thermal Cycler. The tubes were heated to 95°C for 1 minute, 56°C for 1 minute, and 72°C for 1 minute 35 seconds. This cycle was repeated 35 times. The tubes were kept at 72°C for 7 more minutes and then cooled down to 4°C for storage.

After PCR, gel electrophoresis was conducted to check the molecular size of the PCR product. First, the gel was made. The gel was composed of agarose (Biosharp) and 1x Tris-acetate-EDTA buffer (TAE, diluted from the Tsingke TSG001). The gel mixture was put into the microwave and heated until the TAE boiled. The mixture was kept in the microwave for 15 more seconds and was then taken out of the microwave. 5 μL TS-GelRed dye (Tsingke) was added to the mixture, which was then poured into a mould with a gel comb. The gel then solidified over the course of about 30 minutes. After the gel was made, the comb was removed, and the gel was placed in a pool of TAE in the tank. 5 μL of DL2000 Plus DNA Ladder was placed into a well on each piece of gel. 5 μL of each of the samples was placed into one of the other wells. The gel was then moved so that the direction in which the DNA moved was parallel to the sides of the tank. The power was turned on to 150 V. After some time, the power was turned off, and the gel was placed in the Ultra Slim LED Illuminator. The gel was photographed.

2.2. Validation of Barnacle COI Specific (Barn-COI) Primers

Barnacle COI specific primers (Barn-COI) were designed based on the COI sequences of Cirripedia, Copepoda, Decapoda and Isopoda species, which were downloaded from the NCBI nucleotide database. The sequences were aligned using the Muscle algorithm on MEGA 7. The alignment was searched manually for barnacle-specific regions. The length, GC content and T_m of the barnacle-

Figure 1: The morphology of barnacle species examined in this study: a. *Amphibalanus amphitrite*; b. *Megabalanus volcano*; c. *Megabalanus tintinnabulum*; d. *Amphibalanus reticulatus*; e. *Capitulum mitella*; f. *Balanus trigonus*; g. *Chthamalus malayensis*; h. *Megabalanus coccopoma*.

specific regions were calculated using the [NEB Tm Calculator](#). The sequences with the most suitable length, GC content and Tm were chosen and made into candidate primers. The reverse primers were designed by reverse complementing barnacle-specific regions using [Reverse Complement on Bioinformatics.org](#).

The samples were collected. In addition to the samples used in the Barn-18s validation experiments, *Megabalanus coccopoma* and *Amphibalanus amphitrite* were collected from Qixingwan (22.567875°N, 114.531134°E).

The DNA was extracted in the same way as in the Barn-18s validation experiments.

PCR was conducted in almost the same way as in the Barn-18s validation experiments. However, the PCR mix used was the Tsingke TSE002 2x Tsingke Master Mix (Green), and the annealing temperature was 52°C instead of 56°C. All non-barnacle samples were also mixed together. All other steps were identical to the Barn-18s experiments.

Gel electrophoresis was also conducted similarly to the Barn-18s validation experiments, except that the marker used was the Tsingke DL5000 instead of the DL2000 Plus DNA Ladder. All other steps were identical to the Barn-18s experiments.

2.3. Validation of *M. coccopoma* COI Specific (Cocc-COI) Primers

M. coccopoma COI specific primers (Cocc-COI) were designed based on the COI sequences of *M. coccopoma* and other barnacle species, including *Megabalanus tintinnabulum*, *Megabalanus volcano*, *Amphibalanus reticulatus*, *Amphibalanus amphitrite*, *Balanus trigonus*, *Capitulum mitella* and *Chthamalus malayensis* (Fig. 1), which were downloaded from the NCBI nucleotide database. The sequences were aligned using the Muscle algorithm on MEGA 7. The alignment was searched manually for *M. coccopoma*-specific regions. The length, GC content and Tm of the *M. coccopoma*-specific regions were calculated using [NEB Tm Calculator](#). The sequences with the most suitable length,

Figure 2: Map of the area around Shenzhen showing the locations where plankton samples were collected.

GC content and Tm were chosen and made into the following primers. The reverse primers were designed by reverse complementing *coccopoma*-specific regions using [Reverse Complement on Bioinformatics.org](#).

The same samples were used as in the Barn-COI validation experiments.

PCR was conducted on the samples in the same way as for the Barn-COI validation experiments, except that all non-*M. coccopoma* samples were mixed together, instead of just non-barnacle samples.

The gel electrophoresis was conducted the same way as with the Barn-COI experiments.

2.4. Application of Cocc-COI primers on plankton samples

Plankton samples were collected at Qixingwan (22.567875°N, 114.531134°E), Yangmeikeng (22.549431°N, 114.565043°E), Qian'ai (22.567573°N, 114.459729°E) and Beizaijiao (22.600541°N, 114.346604°E) (Fig. 2) using a plankton net with a net pore size of 30 µm. The samples from Qian'ai were collected from water 3-4 m deep, while the rest were collected from the surface. The samples were stored in 75% alcohol. The DNA was extracted in the same way as for the Barn-18s experiments, except that 0.1 mm glass beads were not added. PCR was conducted the same way as for the Barn-18s validation experiments. The gel electrophoresis was conducted the same way as for the Barn-COI validation experiments.

2.5. Control Experiments

All samples used, including all barnacle samples (*M. coccopoma*, *M. tintinnabulum*, *C. mitella*, *I. cumingi* and *A. amphitrite*), all non-barnacle samples (decapod, fish, cephalopod, gastropod, bivalve) and plankton samples (from Qixingwan, Qian'ai, Yangmeikeng and Beizaijiao) were tested with the pair of universal primers LCO 1490 and HCO 2198, and with no primers at all. All combina-

tions of the Barn-18s, Barn-COI and Cocc-COI primers, as well as LCO and HCO, were also all tested without samples. For the samples with no primers and tests involving the Barn-18s primers, the PCR cycles previously used for the Barn-18s primers were used. For the tests involving the Barn-COI primers, the PCR cycles previously used for the Barn-COI primers were used. For the tests involving the Cocc-COI primers, the PCR cycles previously used for the Cocc-COI primers were used. For the tests with the HCO and LCO primers, the same PCR cycles were used as Barn-18s, except that the annealing temperature was 40°C rather than 56°C. The marker used was the Solarbio D2000 Plus DNA Ladder for all the control experiments.

3. Results

3.1. Specificity of Barn-COI and Barn-18s Primers

In total, 3 forward and 3 reverse candidate Barn-18s primers were designed as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 3. The 18S regions covered by the Barn-18s primers are shown in Fig. 3. The gel electrophoresis results for the Barn-18s validation experiments performed on barnacle samples are shown in Fig. 4. The DL2000 marker shows bands at 2000 bp, 1000 bp, 750 bp, 500 bp, 250 bp, and 100 bp, of which the band at 750 bp is the brightest.

The gel electrophoresis results showed that all the Barn-18s primer combinations could amplify all of the barnacle samples. Additionally, because the lengths of the DNA strands in the bands corresponded roughly with the lengths of the target regions of the different primer pairs, it is likely that the amplified segments were of the target regions of the 18S gene, with the exception of a non-specific band between 1000-2000 bp from the combination *M. tintinnabulum* + 472F + 1104R (top row of Fig. 4). However, most of the non-barnacle samples were amplified as well, although the amplified segments were not the target region in the 18S gene, with many non-specific bands and smears. This revealed that the Barn-18s primers were not actually specific to barnacles, and could amplify different parts of the genomes of non-barnacle species. There is a small chance, though, that these results may have been caused by contamination or mistakes made when conducting the tests. However, these results showed that the Barn-18s primers are most likely not specific to barnacles. Three forward and 2 reverse candidate Barn-COI primers were also designed based on the COI sequences from multiple barnacle species and copepod references, as shown in Table 2 and Fig. 5. The gel electrophoresis results for the Barn-COI validation experiments are shown in Fig. 6. The DL5000 marker shows bands at 5000 bp, 2000 bp, 1000 bp, 750 bp, 500 bp, 250 bp, and 100 bp, of which the band at 750 bp is the brightest. The results showed that none of the Barn-COI primer combinations could amplify all of the barnacle samples. All primer combinations failed to amplify any bar-

nacle samples, except for 397F + 512R, which successfully amplified the DNA of only the *Capitulum mitella*, *Megabalanus coccopoma*, and *Ibla cumingi* samples (top row of Fig. 6), with the length of the bands roughly corresponding with the length of the target region. This may be because there was too much variation among the COI sequences of different barnacles, making it difficult to design a primer that can successfully amplify all of them. None of the non-barnacle samples were amplified. A plankton sample from Qixingwan was also tested along with the barnacle and non-barnacle samples and was not amplified. Therefore, the Barn-COI primers have been shown to not be able to amplify all barnacle samples.

3.2. Specificity of Cocc-COI Primers

3 forward and 3 reverse candidate Cocc-COI primers were designed based on the multiple sequence alignment result of *M. coccopoma* and other barnacle specifics, as shown in Table 3 and Fig. 7. The gel electrophoresis results for the Barn-COI validation experiments are shown in Fig. 8. The DL5000 marker shows bands at 5000 bp, 2000 bp, 1000 bp, 750 bp, 500 bp, 250 bp, and 100 bp, of which the band at 750 bp is the brightest. These results showed that most combinations of the Cocc-COI primers successfully amplified the target region in samples of *M. coccopoma*. However, all three combinations involving Cocc-COI-197F (top row of Fig. 8) did not produce any bands at all. The mix of non-*M. coccopoma* samples was not amplified, except for by the combination 85F + 331R, which produced a very faint band (bottom row of Fig. 8). However, all other combinations were shown to be able to specifically amplify samples of *M. coccopoma* DNA.

3.3. Application of Cocc-COI Primers on Plankton Samples

A sample from Qixingwan (the same as the sample previously tested with the Barn-COI primers) was also tested along with the *M. coccopoma* and non-*M. coccopoma* samples (Fig. 9, and none were amplified at all, including those shown to be *M. coccopoma*-specific, apparently showing that *M. coccopoma* larvae were not present in the sample. Additionally, one plankton sample from Yangmeikeng, one from Qian'ai, and one from Beizaijiao were also tested with the Cocc-COI primers (as they were the only primers that were shown to function as intended). However, none of these were amplified at all either, again showing that *M. coccopoma* larvae were apparently not present.

3.4. Control Experiments

The gel electrophoresis results for the control experiments are shown in Fig. 10. The D2000 Plus marker shows bands at 5000 bp, 3000 bp, 2000 bp, 1500 bp, 1000 bp, 750 bp, 500 bp, 250 bp, and 100 bp. All samples amplified by the HCO and LCO primers showed a band at around

Figure 3: Simple schematic showing the Barn-18s primers and alignments in MEGA.

Table 1: The sequences of the candidate barnacle-specific 18S primers chosen for this investigation.

Primer name	Sequence	T _m (°C)
Barn-18s-320F	5'-AAATATCTGCCTTATCAGCTC-3'	59
Barn-18s-472F	5'-AGTTCAGGGAGGTAGTGAC-3'	63
Barn-18s-499F	5'-CCTTACAGAGGTCTCGTTAAC-3'	62
Barn-18s-1104R	3'-CATTTCCCTTCGACTCTC-5'	59
Barn-18s-1605R	3'-CGGCGTCAAGTTTAATAG-5'	57
Barn-18s-2031R	3'-GAAAAGGGTTCAAACGTTTG-5'	60

700 bp, the expected size, seemingly except for the *A. amphitrite* sample. All tests with samples or without primers produced no bands, as expected, showing that no DNA regions had been amplified. However, there is a smear present with Barn-COI-397F + 397R, possibly caused by high concentrations of the primers.

4. Discussion

In the experiment, Barn-18s, Barn-COI, and Cocc-COI primers were designed and tested. The Barn-18s primers were proven to be not specific to barnacles, as they all successfully amplified regions of non-barnacle DNA, although these regions appeared not to be part of the 18S rRNA gene. The Barn-COI primers were also shown to be not barnacle-specific, as none successfully amplified the DNA of all barnacle samples, possibly due to the COI sequences of barnacles being very different from each other. However, four pairs of Cocc-COI primers were shown to be *M. coccopoma*-specific, as they only amplified the COI genes of *M. coccopoma* samples.

Indeed, one of the most difficult parts of primer design is choosing a suitable gene. For example, in the experiment, the COI gene was discovered to be less suitable for designing barnacle-specific primers. This is due to large degrees of variation between the sequences of different barnacle species causing difficulties finding regions common to all barnacle species. In this case, using an even more conservative gene such as 18S may be easier, although in this case the regions chosen during primer design either were not specific to barnacles or coincided with sections of other genes from other species. However, the COI gene did prove extremely useful for designing *M. coccopoma*-specific primers, as there was enough variation among the different barnacle species for enough *M. coccopoma*-specific regions to be selected. In contrast, the 18S gene, which had been more effective for barnacle-specific primers, was much less useful for *M. coccopoma*-specific primers, as the sequences of *M. coccopoma* and *M. tintinnabulum* were completely identical except for one base, leading to a failed attempt at designing a Cocc-18s

Figure 4: Gel electrophoresis results of the Barn-18s validation experiments.

Table 2: The sequences of the candidate barnacle-specific COI primers chosen for this investigation.

Primer name	Sequence	T _m (°C)
Barn-COI-124F	5'-AGGAAAGATTAATTGGAGATG-3'	56
Barn-COI-321F	5'-TATTATTAATTAGAGGATC-3'	52
Barn-COI-397F	5'-TATTGCTCATTGAGGAG-3'	54
Barn-COI-397R	3'-CTCCTGAATGAGCAATA-5'	54
Barn-COI-512R	3'-CGATCAAATGTAAAGTTTC-5'	54

Figure 5: Simple schematic showing the Barn-COI primers and alignments on MEGA. Due to low resolution, the letters of the sequences may not display properly, but Red represents T, Purple G, Green A, and Blue C.

Table 3: The sequences of the candidate *M. coccopoma*-specific COI primers chosen for this investigation.

Primer name	Sequence	Tm (°C)
Cocc-COI-28F	5'-GTCAGCTATAGTAGGTAC-3'	54
Cocc-COI-85F	5'-AGGTAGTTTAATTGGAGATG-3'	56
Cocc-COI-197F	5'-TTATTACCCCTAATGCTAGGG-3'	60
Cocc-COI-270R	3'-AAAAGTATTAGAGCAGGAG-5'	55
Cocc-COI-331R	3'-ATAAGGGAGGATAAACAGTC-5'	58
Cocc-COI-532R	3'-CTGGTAAAGAAAGAAGTAATAAA-5'	55

primer, before the Cocc-COI primers were designed.

According to the experiment results, *M. coccopoma* DNA was not detected in plankton samples from any of the four tested locations. This could lead to several possibilities regarding whether or not *M. coccopoma* is established in Shenzhen. The first possibility is that *M. coccopoma* is indeed not reproducing, and therefore not established in any of the four locations. This would indicate that there is currently no threat of invasion of the area by *M. coccopoma*. However, this possibility seems quite unlikely, as large numbers of adult individuals of *M. coccopoma* were spotted during plankton sample collection, at least in Qixingwan and Qian'ai. A second possibility is that there are, in fact, *M. coccopoma* larvae present in the water in at least some of the locations tested, but they were not collected in the samples. This was likely not caused by seasonal factors, as *M. coccopoma* reproduces year-round [9], but may be caused by extremely low concentrations of larvae in the

water, which caused none of them to be captured due to the limited size of samples taken. The absence of *M. coccopoma* larvae in the plankton samples could also have been caused by the larvae not being present near the surface of the water and instead being located in the deeper layers, so they were not able to be collected. If this possibility is true, further investigations with larger sample sizes will be needed to determine whether or not *M. coccopoma* is truly established.

Although the Cocc-COI primers, despite being successfully validated to be specific to *M. coccopoma*, were not able to determine whether or not *M. coccopoma* is established around Shenzhen, due to limited sample size, it could potentially more reliably determine this if much more extensive sample collection were performed. With a large enough sample, the Cocc-COI primers could potentially detect larvae of *M. coccopoma* and confirm or provide evidence against the establishment of *M. coccopoma* in certain

Figure 7: Simple schematic showing the Cocc- COI primers and alignments on MEGA.

Figure 8: Gel electrophoresis results of the Cocc-COI validation experiments.

Figure 9: Gel electrophoresis results of the tests of plankton samples from Qixingwan using Cocc-COI Primers.

Figure 10: Gel electrophoresis results of the positive and negative control experiments.